

GlaS - - Fuels

Single-Atom Photocatalysts Enhanced by a Self-Powered Photonic Glass Reactor to Produce Advanced Biofuels

5 Partners | 4 Countries | 2.99M Total Budget | 42 Months

Tangible Impact

SOCIAL

Increased biofuel production
with a mission to expand
renewable energy

ENVIRONMENTAL

Reduction in CO₂ emissions

Use of bioethanol produced
from bio-waste

ECONOMIC

Introduction of biobutanol as
a cutting-edge transportation
biofuel

Alternative pathway for green
hydrogen production

Boost in bioethanol demand

Job growth in the biofuels
industry

 @glasafuels
 GlaS-A-Fuels Project
 www.glas-a-fuels-project.eu
 glasafuels@gmail.com